

PRISMA-P (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic review and Meta-Analysis Protocols) 2015 checklist: recommended items to address in a systematic review protocol*

Section and topic	Item No	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
ADMINISTRATIVE INFORMATION			
Title:			
Identification	1a	Identify the report as a protocol of a systematic review	<i>Title (“Protocol for a Systematic Review…”).</i>
Update	1b	If the protocol is for an update of a previous systematic review, identify as such	<i>Not applicable — not an update.</i>
Registration	2	If registered, provide the name of the registry (such as PROSPERO) and registration number	<i>Title page and Abstract (“Systematic review registration”): PROSPERO CRD420261322905.</i>
Authors:			
Contact	3a	Provide name, institutional affiliation, e-mail address of all protocol authors; provide physical mailing address of corresponding author	<i>Title page (authors, affiliations, e-mails, ORCID; corresponding-author address).</i>
Contributions	3b	Describe contributions of protocol authors and identify the guarantor of the review	<i>Declarations — Author contributions (guarantor: DJ).</i>
Amendments	4	If the protocol represents an amendment of a previously completed or published protocol, identify as such and list changes; otherwise, state plan for documenting important protocol amendments	<i>Title page (“Protocol amendments” statement); not an amendment. Amendments will be logged and dated in the PROSPERO record and in</i>

revised article versions.

Support:

Sources	5a	Indicate sources of financial or other support for the review	<i>Declarations — Funding.</i>
Sponsor	5b	Provide name for the review funder and/or sponsor	<i>Declarations — Funding (EU Horizon Europe MSCA PF, GA No 101211169; University of Malta).</i>
Role of sponsor or funder	5c	Describe roles of funder(s), sponsor(s), and/or institution(s), if any, in developing the protocol	<i>Declarations — Funding (“The funder had no role...”).</i>

INTRODUCTION

Rationale	6	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of what is already known	<i>Section 1 (Background).</i>
Objectives	7	Provide an explicit statement of the question(s) the review will address with reference to participants, interventions, comparators, and outcomes (PICO)	<i>Section 1 (closing) and Section 2.1 with Table 1 (PICO); Abstract.</i>

METHODS

Eligibility criteria	8	Specify the study characteristics (such as PICO, study design, setting, time frame) and report characteristics (such as years considered, language, publication status) to be used as criteria for eligibility for the review	<i>Section 2.1 and Table 1; Sections 2.1.1–2.1.7.</i>
Information sources	9	Describe all intended information sources (such as electronic databases, contact with study authors, trial registers or other grey literature sources) with planned dates of coverage	<i>Section 2.2 and Table 2; Section 2.2.1; coverage 1 Jan 2010 – 31 Jan 2026.</i>
Search strategy	10	Present draft of search strategy to be used for at least one electronic database, including planned limits, such that it could be repeated	<i>Sections 2.3.1–2.3.4 (full draft search strings for PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, IEEE Xplore).</i>

Study records:

Data management	11a	Describe the mechanism(s) that will be used to manage records and data throughout the review	<i>Section 2.4 (Rayyan; deduplication and record management).</i>
Selection process	11b	State the process that will be used for selecting studies (such as two independent reviewers) through each phase of the review (that is, screening, eligibility and inclusion in meta-analysis)	<i>Section 2.4 (two-stage screening; independent reviewers; third-reviewer adjudication; PRISMA 2020 flow diagram).</i>
Data collection process	11c	Describe planned method of extracting data from reports (such as piloting forms, done independently, in duplicate), any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators	<i>Section 2.5 (independent dual extraction; piloting on five studies; Cohen's kappa). Instrument provided as Extended data.</i>
Data items	12	List and define all variables for which data will be sought (such as PICO items, funding sources), any pre-planned data assumptions and simplifications	<i>Section 2.5 (72-variable instrument; token conventions). Full instrument provided as Extended data (Zenodo).</i>
Outcomes and prioritization	13	List and define all outcomes for which data will be sought, including prioritization of main and additional outcomes, with rationale	<i>Section 2.1.4 (primary outcome AUC; secondary outcomes; prioritization and rationale).</i>
Risk of bias in individual studies	14	Describe anticipated methods for assessing risk of bias of individual studies, including whether this will be done at the outcome or study level, or both; state how this information will be used in data synthesis	<i>Section 2.6 (PROBAST+AI primary, four domains; QUADAS-2 secondary; applicability axis). RoB form provided as Extended data.</i>
Data synthesis	15a	Describe criteria under which study data will be quantitatively synthesised	<i>Section 2.8 (comparability criteria; I² threshold).</i>

	15b	If data are appropriate for quantitative synthesis, describe planned summary measures, methods of handling data and methods of combining data from studies, including any planned exploration of consistency (such as I^2 , Kendall's τ)	Section 2.8 (bivariate random-effects model; I^2 and Tau^2 ; strata by tier and predictor timing).
	15c	Describe any proposed additional analyses (such as sensitivity or subgroup analyses, meta-regression)	Section 2.8 (pre-specified subgroups; two sensitivity analyses; meta-regression).
	15d	If quantitative synthesis is not appropriate, describe the type of summary planned	Section 2.8 (narrative synthesis following SWiM).
Meta-bias(es)	16	Specify any planned assessment of meta-bias(es) (such as publication bias across studies, selective reporting within studies)	Section 2.8 (Deeks' funnel-plot test; qualitative small-study and reporting-bias assessment).
Confidence in cumulative evidence	17	Describe how the strength of the body of evidence will be assessed (such as GRADE)	Section 2.9 (GRADE-DTA across five domains).

*** It is strongly recommended that this checklist be read in conjunction with the PRISMA-P Explanation and Elaboration (cite when available) for important clarification on the items. Amendments to a review protocol should be tracked and dated. The copyright for PRISMA-P (including checklist) is held by the PRISMA-P Group and is distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution Licence 4.0.**

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